

23rd EBES CONFERENCE - MADRID PROCEEDINGS

SEPTEMBER 27-29, 2017
MADRID, SPAIN

HOSTED BY

FACULTY OF ECONOMICS AND BUSINESS
UNIVERSIDAD COMPLUTENSE DE MADRID

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Skill Mismatch Analysis on the Labour Market in Serbia

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Abstracts: *The globalization process and permanent technological changes have brought major transformations in labour markets. The labour market has become more dynamic, while job creation and job destruction rate increased significantly. The emergence of new jobs in parallel with the disappearance of the old ones has led to changes in labour demand by employers. A growing demand for new skills and consequently smaller demand for traditional skills have produced skill mismatch on the labour market. In transitional economies, the problem of a skill mismatch has been even more pronounced, because of privatization and restructuring process. Serbia, as one of the transitional countries, has experienced severe economic and institutional reform that led to poor labour market performance and increasing gap between qualifications demanded by employers and qualifications supplied by workers. The goal of our paper is to estimate the volume of skill mismatch on the Serbian labour market and to analyze is there any gender aspect related to it. In that purpose, we will use a couple of indicators calculated from the internationally standardized questionnaire LFS – variance of unemployment and a share of the specific educational group in a number of total unemployed and total employed persons. The results are showing that skill mismatch on the labour market exists, especially for those with secondary education. Furthermore, skill mismatch is more emphasized between women with secondary education than between men with the same degree and the global economic crisis did not contribute to the expansion of skill mismatch on the labour market.*

Keywords: *Skill Mismatch, Labour Market, Serbia, Qualification*

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Section 1: Introduction

In the past few decades, labour markets have experienced major reshuffling. New technological revolution and the rise of globalization process have had its influence on the type of skills demanded by employers. Unfavorable demographical trend - displayed by the aging of the population, in combination with expansion of new skills and technology, have resulted in a labour market situation where it is troublesome to pair the right workers with the right jobs. Recent OECD study confirms the existence of skill mismatch on the labour market, as about 21% of workers are over-qualified and 13% are under-qualified for their jobs, which has a significant impact on wages and productivity (OECD, 2013).

A similar situation can be found within EU countries. To raise awareness about growing skill mismatch, the European Commission adopted “A new Skills Agenda for Europe” (EC, 2016). The Commission invites Members States, social partners, the industry and other stakeholders to work together to (1) improve the quality and relevance of skills formation, (2) make skills more visible and comparable and (3) improve skills intelligence and information for better career choices. Current agenda just following the line of thought of the earlier initiative of the European Commission “New Skills for New Jobs – anticipating and matching labour market and skills needs” (EC, 2008).

In transitional economies, the problem of a skill mismatch has been even more pronounced. Different kind of skill surpluses and skill shortages emerges in the transitional countries due to privatization and restructuring process. The essence of the transition process involves the destruction of old jobs and the creation of new ones, which mostly require different set of skill from those that have been destroyed. The main problem for those countries is that existing education and training system can not keep pace with growing demand for new skills. On the other hand, there is no longer a need for part of the skills produced by the socialist educational system. Both facts have a significant influence in widening skill gap – first leading to skill shortages and later leading to skill surpluses (ETF, 2013).

The Serbia is not an exception. From 2000 - which is marked as a starting year (at least nominally) of the transition process in Serbia - until the beginning of the economic crisis, Serbian economy recorded relatively high rate of economic growth. However, GDP growth was not followed by the growth in employment, which led to negative values of employment elasticity³. In addition to structural issues and an inadequate privatization model, the insufficient skill level required for finding a job in a new, capitalist system, was a major constraint for employment growth. The financial crisis contributed to an already

³ Employment elasticity is defined as a percentage change in the number of employed persons in an economy compared with a percentage change in the economic output, measured by the gross domestic product.

difficult matching process because the lack of sufficient jobs vacancies and an increase in on-job requirements demanded by employers. In the continuation of our paper, we will use several different measures to estimate the volume of skill mismatch in Serbia, as well as how much has economic crisis contributed to widening/narrowing that mismatch.

After the introduction, the rest of our paper is structured in the following way. In Section 2, we present the basic labour market indicators for different demographical and educational groups and their trend since the beginning of the global economic crisis. Section 3 is reserved for an explanation of used methodology and data sources. In Section 4 we present main results from our calculation, which is followed by Section 5 where we make a conclusion and final recommendation for policymakers.

Section 2: Labour market in Serbia

Like many developing economies, labour market performances in Serbia is notably lagging behind the most developed EU countries and OECD countries. The labour market in Serbia is distinguished by the relatively low level of labour-force participation, high unemployment rate and a large number of those who are not in education, employment, or training (NEET). The employment rate is moderate, but according to the quality of employment, Serbia is far beyond any developed country. The high rate of informality, a large share of vulnerable employment and employment on temporary contracts with growing trend of precarious employment, being some of the factors that speak in favor of low employment quality. Moreover, since entering in transition, the labour market in Serbia has been very segmented with some groups having extremely unfavorable position comparing to the working-age population. In Table 1 we provide main indicators of the labour market in Serbia for different cohorts.

Table 1 – The basic indicators of labour market in Serbia

		2008		2012		2016 ⁴	
		e'	u'	e'	u'	e'	u'
Total	15-64	53.7	14.4	45.3	24.6	55.2	15.9
	Female	45.3	16.7	38.1	25.6	48.4	16.7
	15-24	21.1	35.2	14.5	51	19.7	34.9
Education level	Low	33.1	11	22.7	22.6	27.8	12.4
	Middle	52.9	16.3	43.1	26.8	49.8	16.7
	High	64.6	8.8	53.6	17	60.5	13.9
Type of settlement	Urban	50.7	16.1	43.4	27	53.5	17.9
	Rural	58.1	12.1	47.9	21.3	57.8	12.9

Source: LFS, SORS.

Looking at the pre-crisis values of unemployment and employment rates for different groups (1) it confirms the hypothesis of highly fragmented labour market and (2) indicates the extent of lagging behind EU 28 averages. Regarding the first, the employment rate for women in 2008 was around 6 p.p. lower than the working-age population average, meaning that gap between female and male employment rate is much more pronounced. The youngest (15-24) are even in more compounded position having employment rate almost three times lower than working-age population. While education seems to be a very effective strategy for employment opportunity, since employment rate rises with educational level, it does not provide protection against unemployment. In all three presented years, the unemployment rate of those with secondary education is notably higher than for other two educational levels. Potential causes for this circumstances lie in the nature of restructuring process where job destruction was most prominent for an industrial worker who holds a secondary degree. An additional reason for the vulnerability of those with a secondary degree could be secondary schools which do not equip students with a type of skills that would make them attractive to employers. On the other side, unexpectedly lower unemployment rate for those with primary or no education could be explained by (1) high inactivity rate of these group, (2) high level of informal employment (mainly in agriculture and construction) and (3) higher employment and lower unemployment rate in rural area, where this cohort is predominantly settled. Leaning on the previous, labour market indicators in Serbia once again prove that unemployment is an urban phenomenon, with unemployment rate higher for 4-6 p.p. during analyzed span than in rural area.

Secondly, by comparison, total employment rate and employment rate of females for EU 28 in 2008 was around 66% and 59%, respectively, which is 13 p.p. higher than in Serbia. Even greater differences could

⁴ The weighting procedure in LFS was changed by the SORS in 2014. It caused the break in time series. However, change in procedure would affects mostly absolute numbers, making comparison of calculated rates methodologically correct.

be found in employment rate by educational level. The biggest fall behind in 2008 is recorded for highly educated people in Serbia, where they lagged around 20 p.p. behind EU 28 averages, which is followed by middle and low educated ones lagging around 15 p.p.⁵.

Further analysis of data presented in Table 1 showing that since the start of the global economic crisis in 2008, the labour market in Serbia has gone through two subperiods - deterioration period 2008-2012, and recovery period 2012-2016. Almost all of the above-presented indicators followed the path of „U“ shape (or inverted „U“ shape when we are looking at unemployment rate). Namely, it is clear that economic crisis unanimously worsened the position of all groups on the labour market. However, some of those groups worsened an already difficult pre-crisis position. The global crisis most affected youngest which employment rate in 2016 was still around 1.5 p.p. lower than before 8 years. Similarly, all education levels worsened their positions and are still behind its pre-crisis level of employment rate, with highest and lowest educated people suffered the most.

All being said aiming to provide a wider picture of the situation on the labour market in Serbia since the beginning of the global crisis, but conclusions on skill match still can be drawn. To estimate the volume of skill mismatch first, we need to define an appropriate methodology. The introduction of different concepts of skill mismatch and methods for measuring it will be tackled in next section.

Section 3: Methodology and Data

The inadequate skill matching process has brought the attention of scientific public in last quarter of 20th century when the study conducted by Richard Freeman (Freeman, 1976) found that income returns from college graduates in the USA continuously declined since 1970. He argues that overeducation will become growing phenomenon in modern society and that oversupply of college-educated workforce would leave a notable distortion on the labour market. For more than two decades, the problem of skill mismatch was put aside, because investments (both private and public) in education was universally preached medicine for rapid economic development. The problem of skill mismatch surfaced again in the late 1990s with the emergence of new technological revolution, when the first instruments for measuring its volume appeared.

For measuring the skill mismatch, a multidimensional approach is required, because there is no unique definition of it. According to (Cedefop, 2015) we differentiate various types of skill mismatches:

⁵ Eurostat.

1. General mismatch - A situation where industries, occupations, locations or groups with different levels of education/skill differ in the ratio of unemployment to vacancies.
2. Over-qualification - A situation in which an individual has a higher qualification than his/her job requires.
3. Under-qualification - A situation in which an individual has a lower qualification than his/her current job requires.
4. Over-skilling (or skill underutilization) - A situation in which an individual is not able to utilize fully his or her skills and abilities in the current job.
5. Under-skilling - A situation in which an individual lacks the skills and abilities necessary to perform the current job adequately.
6. Skill shortage - A situation where demand for a particular type of skill exceeds the supply of that skill at the prevailing rate of pay.
7. Skill deficit - A situation where the skills and abilities of individuals are lower than a given benchmark level of skills.

In addition to various types of skill mismatches, there are at least three dimensions of it:

- Vertical versus Horizontal
- Macro versus Micro
- Demand for skill on the labour market versus Supply of skill from the education and training system

The vertical mismatch refers to various types of mismatch between the level of existing and required education (qualifications) and/or skills, typically expressed as 'low', 'medium' and 'high' skills or qualifications. In other words, a graduate is not employed in a graduate level job, but in one suitable for a person with a lower level of qualification. It can result from a set of qualifications that are too high for the job (over-education) or too low for the requirements of the job (under-education).

The horizontal mismatch is rather concerned by the area/field of knowledge-skills, not with the level of qualifications/skills – a person may have the required level of qualifications/skills for the job, but the wrong (inadequate) type/area of knowledge for that job. A typical example is when a graduate is not employed in the qualification he or she has studied, even if employed in a graduate level job.

Macro versus micro referring to an aspect of analysis – first approach using aggregate (macro) data, while later is based on various types of employers (micro) survey. The last dimension indicates the side of the issue of skill mismatch. One can focus on shortcomings of educational and training system, while other is based on issues coming from demand side on the labour market.

In our paper, we will use a combination of data from two sources – Labour Force Survey (LFS) and National Employment Services (NES). The main source for our analysis will be internationally standardized questionnaire LFS, which as a household survey provides information not only on the quantity, but also on the quality of employment and its demographic aspect. We will use an absolute number of unemployed and employed persons and calculate appropriate rates to estimate the existence of skill mismatch across various demographic groups. Our main focus certainly will be on differences across educational levels, but also gender aspect will be included. Until 2013, Serbian LFS separated six types of qualifications: (1) no formal education, (2) incomplete primary school, (3) primary school, (4) secondary school, (5) higher school/college and (6) university faculty, academy, etc. Due to the methodological changes back in 2014, data are now being published only by four qualification levels: (1) no formal education, (2) low, (3) medium and (4) high level of education. In order to ensure time comparability, we will aggregate all individual data to three broad qualification levels – low, medium and high, with low consisting of the first three mentioned categories, and high including the last two categories before the methodological change occurred.

However, although LFS is a superior source for detailed information about employment and unemployment, data for unemployed people by sections of activities are not publicly available, but they are crucial for measuring the intensity of skill mismatch in three main sectors – agriculture, industry and services. For that purpose, we will use NES data on registered unemployed persons which are available for all 21 sections of activities. First, we will aggregate those data in the above-mentioned three broad sectors and then cross them with LFS data on employed persons by sections of activities in order to estimate the volume of skill mismatch.

In accordance with available data, we could not measure every aspect of skill mismatch. The combination of LFS and NES data allows us to estimate the presence of vertical skill mismatch. To examine the level of horizontal skill mismatch, conducting specific types of employer survey or tracer and school leaver surveys are required. Only using data from this kind of sources could allow us to study a mismatch between skills possessed by employees and skills required in the workplace.

A couple of indicators will be used for estimation of a skill mismatch at the labour market in Serbia – variance of relative unemployment rates and share of unemployed people with a given education level to the share of employed people with the same level of education⁶.

⁶ Both indicators were developed by European Training Foundation (ETF)

3.1. Variance of relative unemployment rates

Regardless of the type of data, the variance is a statistical instrument used for measuring how far a set of numbers are spread out from their mean. In our case, we will apply variance on unemployment data of different educational groups. This methodology has a wide use in measuring regional or demographic differences of unemployment rate, i.e. (OECD, 2000). Technically, the unemployment rate of every educational group will be put in relation with the unemployment rate of working-age population. Furthermore, the variance will be applied on thus obtained ratios, which, in case it is positive will imply that skill mismatch exists. Though positive values of variance are implying the presence of skill mismatch, it does not show us what type of mismatch is in place. In other words, using this measure we will only find out is there a presence of education mismatch on the labour market in Serbia, but we will not know is it horizontal or vertical. Additionally, greater values of variance indicate larger differences of the unemployment rate of the observed education groups, and contrary, if the variance is zero, means that the unemployment rate of every observed education group is the same.

3.2. Share of unemployed people with a given education level to the share of employed people with the same level of education

Unlike the first measure, differences between the share of unemployed and share of employed people with the same level of education, primarily measuring vertical skill mismatch. This indicator measuring is there a surplus or a deficit of work force for every educational group. If unemployment share of given educational group is greater than employment share for the same group, the supply of workers with given level of education is higher than demand for them and mismatch is positive. When the opposite is true, demand for workers with given level of education is higher, and mismatch is negative. Skill mismatch would not exist only if the shares of particular education group in both unemployment and employment are identical. However, interpretation of results highly depends on initial assumption about no substitutability of workers. It means that there is no substitution between workers with different levels of education. In other words, workers would rather stay unemployed than accept a job which requires level of education lower than they possess. If this assumption is fulfilled, results of the measure will point out the intensity of vertical skill gap and skill shortages in Serbia. If we neglect no substitutability assumption and allow workers with lower education to be substituted for those with higher one, our measure will suggest the systemic existence of the overeducation problem. In the literature there are different views of this hypothesis, while some speak of the high presence of substitution (Duncan and Hoffman, 1981), others entirely reject it (Groot, 1993).

Section 4: Results

In this section, we will present main results from available data. The value of our first indicator, which is a variance of the unemployment rate for different education groups, will signalize magnitude of any skill mismatch in general. Time trajectory of variance is presented in Graph 1. External shock caused by the global crisis initially increased the volume of skill mismatch on the labour market in Serbia. After the period of economic recovery skill mismatch significantly decreased and amounted to only 0,03 which is led by a slight increase in the last observed year. The current value of 0,05 it may seem small, but indicates that some variation of the unemployment rate for different educational level in Serbia certainly exists.

Graph 1 - Variance of unemployment rate across different education groups

Source: Authors calculation based on LFS data

Unfortunately, before 2014 only aggregated data for unemployed and employed by the level of education are available. Recently, mentioned data are publishing separately for men and women, so the variance of unemployment rate of different educational group by gender is presented only for 2014 and 2016. Notwithstanding, this two years have been a good proxy for us to get an insight of gender aspect of skill mismatch. Results presented in Graph 1, showing that skill mismatch is more pronounced for males, which have almost six times greater value of the observed indicator. In accordance with total variance, values of variance for males and females rose for about same degree in 2016.

As we said in the previous section, the variance of unemployment rate is a very rough indicator and serve only for pointing out does any kind of skill mismatch exist. For accurate results, more sensitive indicators should be used. A bit more delicate indicator, at least by available data, should be differences between the share of unemployed and the share of employed. Just to remind, negative values of this indicator suggest a deficit of workers with given level of education, and opposite, if values are positive, workers with same educational group surpluses demand on the labour market. As can be seen in Graph 2, there is a strong positive skill mismatch for those having a medium level of education, while people with low and high educational level are characterized by moderate negative skill mismatch. Despite the intensity of a skill mismatch has been very high, on the positive side, we can point out it decreasing aspect in all three broad educational group. Similar to our previous measure, we can argue that the global economic crisis did not enlarge skill mismatch. Moreover, it may play major role in narrowing it, especially when we know that the most critical group (medium educational level) almost halved volume of their gap in last pre-crisis year.

Graph 2 – Differences between the share of unemployed and the share of employed by three education group

Source: Authors calculation based on LFS data

The situation for men and women are quite similar to the general trend of this indicator. Inverted „U“ shape is characterizing both genders. However, it should be noted that skill mismatch is much more pronounced for women, especially for those who finished secondary school. Not only that, but men and women distinct from each other by the trend of skill mismatch also. While men experienced a clear deceleration in skill mismatch for medium and high level of education, situation is quite different for women. Comparing it with

2014, only women with high level of education are succeeded to narrow skill mismatch, while those with medium and especially with low education significantly worsened the previous position.

Graph 3 – Differences between the share of unemployed and the share of employed by three education group and by gender

Source: Authors calculation based on LFS data

Leaving level of education aside, we want to step out and examine the magnitude of sectoral mismatch by applying the same methodology. In that manner, we will scratch the surface of skill mismatch based not only on the level of education, but also on the field of education. Graph 3 showing the existence of strong negative mismatch in Agriculture and moderate positive mismatch in Industry and Services. On the positive side, we can highlight reduction of mismatch in all three broad sectors over observed time. The potential reason for registered trend could be internal migration from rural to urban areas, where newcomers are increasing the total number of unemployed.

Graph 4 – Differences between the share of unemployed and the share of employed by three broad sector

Source: Authors calculation based on combination of LFS and NES data

Besides mismatch by field of education, similar measure could be applied to estimate the volume of regional mismatch. One study that investigated statistical significance of regional differences in selected labour market indicators in Serbia for the 2000-2009 period, found that regional disparities on the labour market were very pronounced (Dragutinović-Mitrović and Bošković, 2009). Also, they found that polarization of regions was particularly expressed in terms of the unemployment rate. Analyzing skill mismatch by four broad regions, we found a similar thing. Negative skill gap in Belgrade region and Region of West Serbia and Šumadija is followed by moderate positive skill mismatch in Vojvodina region and Region of South and East Serbia (the detailed calculation is presented in Annex). Moreover, encouraging fact is a significant reduction in the regional skill mismatch as recently seen.

Section 5: Conclusion

The new technological revolution has caused major transformation on the labour markets. The emergences of new jobs and the occurrence of mass production have led to increased expectations of employers from their workers. Entirely different set of skills starts to be preferred by employers, from which stand out creativity, innovation and working flexibility. The combination of mentioned factors has played an important role in growing dynamization of labor markets crossing over from traditional „life long job“ to a

„life long learning“. This type of development inevitably led to an acceleration in skill gap. The Recent adoption of numerous agendas and strategies with the intention of tackling growing skill gap in many developed countries, speaks in favor of this case. On the other hand, in most of developing and in all underdeveloped countries this problem is even more pronounced, since the presence of structural issues and insufficiently developed educational system are inherent to them.

Why tackling the skill mismatch is so important for policymakers? Despite the presence of moderate mismatch can not be avoidable, higher intensity of it could cause inconceivable consequences for the economy as a whole. Positive skill mismatch, or overeducation, is usually considered as a greater problem than undereducation. The reason is simple, when later occurs worker holds a lower educational qualification than the one required for the job, but he will receive higher wage premium or higher social status compared to what he could have achieved for his level of education. In the other hand, when a worker is matched with a job that requires a level of education that is lower from one he possesses, many economic and social cost could appear. First, on the individual level, overeducation leading to lower levels of productivity, lower wages, lower job satisfaction and lower returns to education compared with those people with the same education who are correctly matched. Second, on aggregate level, a „brain waste“ phenomenon could become an important issue which in the long term can lead to mass emigration, especially between highly educated youth, and consequently transform itself to a „brain drain“ problem. Besides this, waste in terms of investment made in education and missed opportunity to collect taxes that could be collected in the situation when highly educated people are properly matched, are additional costs for the state if overeducation exists.

The situation in Serbia is similar to other developing countries. Additionally, transitional process and armed conflicts first in the early 1990s, then in the late 1990s, had a significant impact on the already bad demographic structure of the population. Combining this factors with the influence of the global crisis and austerity measures (introduced in 2014), which put downward pressure on already extremely low education budgets, place Serbia in a very prone position regarding the skill mismatch. The results that we present in our paper showing the existence of the skill mismatch on the labour market in general, with a variance of unemployment rate of different educational groups amounted to 0.05. However, the downward trend of a variance suggests that the global economic crisis did not contribute to enhancing skill mismatch, at least according to this indicator. Gender aspect of the measure indicates significantly higher variation in unemployment rate between different education groups for men, which is six times higher than for women.

By looking at shares in unemployment and shares in employment across different education groups, we found a strong positive skill mismatch for those with a medium level of education (most of them have finished four-year secondary school). Strong oversupply of those with medium education is followed by

moderate negative skill mismatch for low and high education holders. The main task is to determine does this negative mismatch registered for those with low and high education is a consequence of a presence of vertical skill gap or there is a problem of overeducation in Serbia. The answer lies in the assumption of no substitutability which we introduced earlier. Once again, if we assume that substitutability between workers of different education level does not exist, bigger unemployment share than employment share can be attributed to vertical mismatch, if that is not the case and substitutability exist, overeducation could be a potential source of the disbalance. How to test whether the introduced assumption is valid in the case of Serbia? We need put in context signs of the measure (positive or negative) for every educational group. If the measure is characterized by continuously growing trend (in absolute terms) substitutability will probably be very pronounced on the labour market. In other words, the pattern of indicator values should be as follow: how we are going down in educational levels values of the indicator must rise (in absolute terms). It means that if those with a medium level of education is squeezed out by those with higher one, than those with low educational level should be squeezed out by workers with secondary education. The results are showing a different pattern of observed indicator – inverted „U“ shape pattern, which indicates that substitutability is not so pronounced on the labour market in Serbia. Consequently, we can argue that, when it comes to skill mismatch, overeducation of the high skilled worker could not be a potential source of the problem. The source of disproportionality between unemployment and employment shares predominantly can be explained by a serious problem of skills shortages in Serbia. However, results of the measure that we proposed should be taken with extreme caution and should be supplemented by other sources which are designed to determine the exact type of the skill mismatch – employers survey.

Analyzing gender aspect of the skill mismatch, we found that it follows a similar pattern like one for the total population, while skill mismatch has been slightly more pronounced for women at every education group. Although inverted „U“ shape of skill mismatch by gender follow a similar pattern of the total population, the trend in time has been different. While men reduced skill mismatch for the observed three year period across all education levels, only high educated women have success in it. The skill mismatch for both low and medium educated women have expanded, which can be a major problem if the trend does not reverse soon.

The presence of a skill mismatch in Serbia is still at a moderate level. However, if policymakers do not work continuously on reducing it, major consequences on the economy as a whole will be inevitable. The problem arises due to the inappropriate curricula and teaching methods used in many high schools and faculties. There is impression that universities open new MBA and MSc programmes not based on labour market needs, but predominantly on what can be offered by the existing knowledge of the university academic staff. To tackle this problem, substantial reform of the educational system is needed. Many out

of date curricula should be replaced, new innovative and attractive curricula must be developed, while existing educational profile should be reorganized to fit better the changing needs of the labor market. Besides reforms of the educational system, active labour market policy should be more efficient in pairing unemployed workers with unfilled vacancies. Also, within active labour market measures different courses should be organized (computer courses, language courses, etc.), especially for those with a low level of education, which will improve their competencies and make them more attractive to employers. On the other hand, internship programs should be provided for those with the highest education. This will give them priceless on-job experience which will later smother their transition from school to work.

The presence of skill mismatch is a very complex problem and can not be straightforwardly solved. It can cause plenty of economic, demographic and social consequences. More complex approach is needed precisely because of that. Different institution at the highest level should be included. Only their mutual cooperation and highly coordinated actions can put this problem under control.

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Annex

Table 1 – Employment and unemployment shares by different demographic characteristics

	2008			2010			2012			2014revised			2016		
	E	U		E	U		E	U		E	U		E	U	
No formal education	1.05	0.72	-0.33	0.71	0.20	-0.51	0.46	0.34	-0.12	0.45	0.54	0.09	0.28	0.07	-0.21
Incomplete primary school	7.76	2.59	-5.16	6.51	1.52	-5.00	5.05	2.45	-2.61	joint data			joint data		
Primary school	17.24	17.01	-0.23	15.73	16.06	0.34	15.11	16.32	1.22	18.32	16.05	-2.27	18.15	14.16	-3.99
Secondary school	55.56	68.44	12.88	56.44	69.10	12.66	56.87	66.26	9.39	57.11	64.71	7.60	56.77	63.24	6.47
Higher school/college	6.57	5.24	-1.33	6.55	5.22	-1.33	7.24	4.53	-2.71	24.13	18.70	-5.42	24.80	22.21	-2.59
University faculty, academy	11.82	6.00	-5.82	14.06	7.90	-6.17	15.27	10.10	-5.17	joint data			joint data		
Age															
15–24	1.29	6.14	4.85	0.80	3.51	2.71	0.65	3.69	3.04	4.70	17.54	12.83	5.49	16.35	10.86
25–64	92.60	93.76	1.17	94.10	96.34	2.24	95.50	95.93	0.42	90.82	82.29	-8.52	89.37	83.43	-5.94
65 +	6.11	0.09	-6.02	5.10	0.15	-4.95	3.84	0.38	-3.46	4.48	0.17	-4.31	5.14	0.22	-4.92
Gender															
Men	57.10	48.84	-8.26	57.29	54.41	-2.88	58.02	55.77	-2.25	56.80	54.11	-2.69	56.32	53.45	-2.87
Women	42.90	51.16	8.26	42.71	45.59	2.88	41.98	44.23	2.25	43.20	45.89	2.69	43.68	46.55	2.87
Type of settlement															
Urban	53.59	64.25	10.66	54.75	62.69	7.94	54.39	63.47	9.08	57.75	65.16	7.41	57.34	68.12	10.79
Rural	46.41	35.75	-10.66	45.25	37.31	-7.94	45.61	36.53	-9.08	42.25	34.84	-7.41	42.66	31.88	-10.79
Region															
Belgrade region	20.73	21.06	0.33	23.31	17.20	-6.11	22.58	19.53	-3.06	24.00	21.51	-2.49	24.15	24.90	0.76
Vojvodina region	25.59	25.93	0.34	24.87	26.89	2.02	25.49	29.08	3.59	26.25	28.00	1.76	26.11	25.84	-0.26
Region of West serbia and Sumadija	joint data	joint data	joint data	29.91	29.84	-0.07	29.95	27.68	-2.27	29.72	27.11	-2.60	29.03	27.70	-1.33
Region of South and Serbia				21.90	26.07	4.17	21.98	23.71	1.73	20.04	23.38	3.34	20.72	21.55	0.83

Source: Authors calculations based on LFS data